

D5.3

TOOLKIT REPORT FOR DATA SHARING BETWEEN RESEARCHERS AND INSTITUTIONS IN THE FIELD OF LITERARY STUDIES

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April 23, 2024

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101004984

Project Acronym: CLS INFRA

Project Full Title: Computational Literary Studies Infrastructure

Grant Agreement No.: 101004984

Deliverable/Document Information

Deliverable No.: D5.3

Deliverable Title: TOOLKIT REPORT FOR DATA SHARING BETWEEN RESEARCHERS AND INSTITUTIONS IN THE FIELD OF LITERARY STUDIES

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Dissemination Level: PUBLIC

Document History

Version/Date
Version 1.0
23.04.2024

0. Executive Summary

Based on the review of literature on, and real-life challenges to data sharing (the latter informed by a series of conversations with outstanding researchers in CLS), this deliverable provides readily comprehensible and easily implementable recommendations and templates organized along the lines of Research Data Life Cycle. It covers research good practices in the context of CLS corpora and data with regard to:

- planning and designing data
- creating and collecting data
- preparing and enriching data
- preserving and publishing data
- reusing data

The wiki, distributed under Licence CC 0 4.0, addresses complex interactions between CLS researchers and other actors involved in data stewardship (data officers, data providers, technical officers, etc.). In line with the general character of the CLS INFRA project, whose participants attend to the needs of CLS researchers, we adopt the perspective of a scholar in their negotiations with institutions rather than representing an institutional point of view.

The wiki will be updated according to the evolution of Open Science policies and culture, in particular data sharing, while remaining a part of an infrastructural European framework for CLS.

Table of Contents

0. Executive Summary.....	3
1. Challenges to sustainable data sharing.....	5
2. Case Studies (Interviews with Researchers).....	7
2.1. Christof Schöch.....	7
2.2. Corinne Bonnet.....	9
2.3. Andrew Piper.....	11
2.4. Federico Pianzola.....	13
2.5. Maciej Eder.....	15
3. Research Good Practices, FAIR Data and Research Data Life Cycle.....	21
3.1. Planning and Designing Data.....	24
3.2. Creation and Collection of Data.....	27
3.3. Preparation and Enrichment of Data.....	30
3.4. Data Analysis.....	33
3.5. Preserving and Publishing Data.....	34
3.6. Reusing Data.....	37
References.....	39

1. Challenges to sustainable data sharing

Author: Françoise Gouzi

Recent changes in research policy and research funding recognise data sharing as a necessary condition for scientific innovation. Data sharing also accelerates changes of practice on an infrastructural level. Open data mandates (and data management plans) are increasingly becoming conditions of research funding on the European, national, and institutional levels. They impact the working conditions and practices of all researchers within the broader arts and humanities domain, let alone those who identify as digital humanists (see [DARIAH Data Policy](#)).

In November 2023, we launched an online **survey** inviting five researchers working with literary corpora (from early career researchers to established ones, from the CLS Infra project and beyond) to give us insights into their data sharing practices. Their responses, which relate to both **technical** and **culture-related** aspects of CLS research, serve in this wiki as **case studies**, on which we base our recommendations for data sharing between researchers and institutions, formulated in section 3. With those recommendations we try to advocate the values of **openness** of science and **reproducibility** of the results as they materialize in the **FAIR principles** (Wilkinson et al 2016); we strive to apply those broad-ranging principles to the specific situation of CLS researchers. In this short introduction, we use excerpts from these surveys, which we publish in their entirety in section 2.

Researchers constantly face numerous, and often conflicting, **demands** for data availability and reusability, voiced in various research policy recommendations and funding requirements, while struggling at the same time with profuse factors that hinder data sharing, of legal, cultural, infrastructural, and managerial nature. Therefore, although policy makers increase pressure to make data openly available, in reality, only a small fraction of datasets are reused and very few scholarly publications include references to datasets (Borgman et al. 2024). Moreover, resources for maintaining data are scarce.

Following situations are symptomatic for the non-reproducibility of research (desquilbet et al 2019), that coincides with hatling data sharing:

- "I've lost my data and my programming code"
- "My results have changed"
- "My code is not running"
- "My new PhD student is not observing the same effects as her predecessor"

When trying to replicate earlier, non-digital work, there is often neither code (but rather a research method) nor data (just the indication of relevant literary works, sometimes not even specific editions).
[from survey responses]

Legal limitations are the single biggest inhibitor to my research. Contemporary publishing has very strong IP protections limiting what researchers can do and study. [from survey responses]

Data created or collected in CLS may be subject to **copyright** in whole or in part. Legal restrictions can affect not only works of art and literature (including specific editions), but also software or databases, i.e. both material and tools in CLS can be subject to restrictions. Importantly, those restrictions affect research practices according to the territoriality principle. For certain topics, the EU has created an overarching **legal framework**, like the [General Data Protection Regulation \(GDPR\)](#), the [Directive on the Legal Protection of Databases](#), or the [Directive on Copyright in the Digital Single Market](#). These are relevant for text and data mining (TDM) in the research context.

Moreover, a crucial impediment to data sharing and the reproducibility of results amount to a **human factor**, i.e. the lack of trained personnel (Borgman et al. 2024). The human factor impacts "infrastructure durability". For this reason, training data management workforce presents a key challenge for Open Science and the FAIR principles (Borgman et al. 2016).

When we consider **epistemic dimensions** of data sharing, we come across such hindrances like the **distance** (Borgman et al. 2024) between data creators and data reusers (domain distance, methodological distance, curation distance, spatio-temporal distance, etc.). To address the data sharing problems relative to the forms of cooperation, Borgman proposes a new form of **governance**: "building the village", i.e. moving towards a community built from the outset around data sharing and the notion of mutual responsibility (Borgman et al. 2022). We might start establishing our village by formulating **explicit policies** and by **documenting our data collection and modelling choices**:

More and more journals have policies on code and data sharing, e.g. Cultural Analytics but also our own journal, the Journal for Computational Literary Studies. [from survey responses]

Making explicit and documenting all data modeling choices. Available ontologies don't cover all aspects of research data in CLS, e.g. there is a big gap related to narrative and fictional elements. It's important to start using more frequently existing ontologies: CIDOC-CRM, NLP Interchange Format, OntoLex, etc. [from survey responses]

Looking back on our experiences with the corpora of the Slovak novel and the haiku recorded in CLS INFRA deliverable 5.2 ([Case studies in data preparation and sharing](#)), we can also highlight the scarcity of resources and insufficient metadata that, for example, does not allow for identifying a literary genre or style as impediments for data sharing and reuse.

Researchers should be able to **replicate analyses** using the same datasets to validate, and build upon existing findings. Efficient **data management** promotes data sharing and collaboration within the research community. Furthermore, proper data management practices ensure the accuracy and reliability of research findings and the long-term accessibility and usability of data. This is crucial for preserving research outputs and data for future generations so as to avoid losing valuable information.

2. Case Studies (Interviews with Researchers)

2.1. Christof Schöch

1. Could you describe your research project, which required gathering and disseminating a large amount of data?

As the example in this response, I use our project "Zeta and Company" on understanding, modeling, implementing, evaluating and using keyness measures for Computational Literary Studies.

2. How do you discover data that is relevant for your research and which factors help you to assess its quality and trustworthiness?

In this case, the object of study is the French contemporary high-brow and low-brow novel. We have obtained items from a large array of sources: commercially-available EPUB files, freely-available EPUB or HTML files, but mostly we digitise pocket editions of these novels ourselves.

3. What are the scholarly workflows that turn source material into data (extraction, transformation, unifying in a repository, etc.)? How do you develop a shared understanding about data with your collaborators and stakeholders?

We scan the books using a document scanner. The books are destroyed in the process for faster scanning. OCR is then applied, then a transformation to simple XML-TEI. A metadata table is managed using a Google spreadsheet for ease of collaborative editing. The text files are stored in a private Github repository in various file formats (XML-TEI, plain text but also non-readable formats (more on that see below). The novels are selected with the aim of covering several decades equally (1950s-1990s), several sub-genres equally (crime, sentimental, detective and general high-brow), also in combination. Gender of authors plays a role, as well, but author gender is highly skewed depending on genre.

4. What is the effect of legal or regulatory limitations on your research design and execution, as well as on your data sharing procedures? What were your relations with data providers and/or copyright holders?

Virtually all of our texts are subject to copyright and cannot be shared freely. This limits us considerably. As a solution, we create so-called "derived text formats" or "extracted features" from our full texts, for example by randomising the order of the words within segments of a certain size while maintaining the order of the segments, or by replacing a certain proportion of words by their POS tags. Many keyness measures still work quite well with such materials.

5. Do you release your datasets together with your research findings? If yes, in what formats / standards and which repositories? What kind of metadata is used?

Yes, we do, that is standard procedure in all of our projects. Except that in this case, we can only share the code and the "derived text format" version of the texts.

6. How can you facilitate mutual understanding of each other's data within your discipline? Do you have shared vocabularies, ontologies or metadata standards available?

Well, there are some general standards like Dublin Core, CIDOC-CRM, LIDO or (of course) TEI. But for those things that are closely related to literary studies, there are no shared and agreed vocabularies, for example vocabularies, taxonomies or ontologies for things like narrative perspective, genres and sub-genres, poetic forms, etc. In another project, called "Mining and Modeling Text", we approaches this issue to some extent. It is not a major concern in "Zeta and Company".

7. Have you ever approached a support research agent (such as a data steward, librarian, or archivist) and requested for or received their assistance? Could you name them? How cultural heritage professionals (archivists, librarians, museologists, etc.) can support your work?

Not really.

8. Have you ever used tools supporting the principles of Open Science, FAIR or CARE in your Data Management Plan, such as automated FAIR metrics evaluation tools (FAIR enough, the FAIR evaluator, data management platform, or others)?

Not in the "Zeta and company" project, but we did evaluate our corpus in the "Mining and Modeling Text" project. We describe this (informal) process here (in German): Röttgermann, Julia, und Christof Schöch. 2020. "FAIRe Daten in den Literaturwissenschaften? Das Beispiel, Mining and Modeling Text und der französische Roman des 18. Jahrhunderts". Romanistik-Blog. Blog des Fachinformationsdienstes ([blog](#)).

9. Have you ever found it difficult to replicate findings obtained by another researcher or to reuse the data that served as the foundation for those conclusions? What was the main reason behind irreproducibility?

Definitely! I have attempted replicating earlier research a number of times. The challenges are different every time. When trying to replicate earlier, non-digital work, there is often neither code (but rather a research method) nor data (just the indication of relevant literary works, sometimes not even specific editions). In other cases, data and/or code might be difficult to locate. I've also used replication as a teaching method, because students really need to understand the details of a method, and get into the inner workings of data and code, to make it work. For some documentation of these attempts, see [personal site web](#).

10. Are you aware of anyone who has attempted to replicate your findings? Was the endeavor a success?

In fact, sort of. It was not directly an attempt to replicate our findings, but someone re-used our data for a new investigation of the same research question with a new set of methods. Still, it was very cool and shows the usefulness of publishing data. The [re-using paper](#).

11. According to you, has the institutional mindset around sharing data evolved over time? In particular, how did you find the attitudes of publishers, libraries and policy-makers?

Attitudes have definitely changed in the right direction. Certainly with libraries and policy-makers and some publishers. But the big publishers just want to secure their part of the pie of the APC budget or the transformative deals, that's all very negative. Scholars need to take scholarly publishing in our own hands and create the infrastructures and habits for diamond open access.– More and more journals have policies on code and data sharing, e.g. Cultural Analytics but also our own journal, the *Journal of Computational Literary Studies*. I'm very tempted to attempt some full and strict replication attempts on the articles from [our journal] itself. Really that should be part of the reviewing process, but it is not the case yet. – I look at evidence of people having understood and practiced Open Science quite a lot when reviewing applications or funding proposals, but I'm afraid that is not a standard perspective yet.

2.2. Corinne Bonnet

1. Could you describe your research project, which required gathering and disseminating a large amount of data?

The ERC Advanced Grant "Mapping Ancient Polytheisms. Cult Epithets as an Interface between Religious Systems and Human Agency" (MAP ; 2017-2023) deals with the way ancient societies named their gods, using variable appellatives in variable combinations, to shape complex and fluid divine powers. What is at stake is to analyse networks of multifaceted divine powers and their environments, instead of fix and essentialised gods. To understand these dynamics, the MAP project takes into account "onomastic sequences", i.e. combinations of various types of elements (nouns, epithets, titles, sentences, etc.), some of which specific and others shared by different gods and goddesses. These onomastic elements played a strategic role in ritual communication to make it efficient. The MAP project approaches the Greek and West-Semitic onomastic practices through a comparative method, on a long-term scale (1000 BCE – 400 CE), in a truly Mediterranean perspective. The MAP database includes the evidence in Greek and Semitic (Hebrew, Phoenician, Punic, Aramaic, Nataean)

2. How do you discover data that is relevant for your research and which factors help you to assess its quality and trustworthiness?

We collect the data contained in the inscriptions, that is a wide range of documents engraved on stone, ivory, metal, ceramics... like dedications, laws, ritual norms, funerary or honorific inscriptions, legends on coins, etc. We systematically analyse the epigraphic corpus of edited inscriptions and many different articles or books containing editions of inscriptions and we select the relevant material; that is inscriptions containing divine names. We assess the quality of the data through different criteria: is the inscription complete? is it perfectly readable? understandable? We read different editions, when available, we compare and choose the more reliable ones.

3. What are the scholarly workflows that turn source material into data (extraction, transformation, unifying in a repository, etc.)? How do you develop a shared understanding about data with your collaborators and stakeholders?

We take a corpus (a book or a digital corpus), we look at all the texts, we select the relevant one, we study them to assess the quality of the data, using other publications, then we register the data in the database. We discuss during our team meeting (every week) all the problematic issues. Before we put the data in open access in the database we check it a second time. We have precise Guidelines for registering the data. We wrote it together and we update them regularly.

4. What is the effect of legal or regulatory limitations on your research design and execution, as well as on your data sharing procedures? What were your relations with data providers and/or copyright holders?

I don't see any obstacle since we are working with the edited material only and we give the reference to the publications we use.

5. Do you release your datasets together with your research findings? If yes, in what formats / standards and which repositories? What kind of metadata is used?

Our database in SQL is completely in open access on Huma-Num. We are preparing a complete data deposit on Nakala too. The format will be CSV. This is the format of our 5 query interfaces. All the metadata are available (for example on the datation, location, support, agents, contexts of the inscriptions)

6. How can you facilitate mutual understanding of each other's data within your discipline? Do you have shared vocabularies, ontologies or metadata standards available?

For the epigraphic material and the XML digital corpus, there are some ontologies available. We used them of course, but we adapted them to our specific needs.

7. Have you ever approached a support research agent (such as a data steward, librarian, or archivist) and requested for or received their assistance? Could you name them? How cultural heritage professionals (archivists, librarians, museologists, etc.) can support your work?

Yes I found excellent support in my University concerning open data and open science with the (Data Steward) and the (Open Science Officer). The first one is helping me with the Nakala issue. We also had excellent support from the librarians of the university. They agreed to give us a long-term loan for the epigraphic corpus, which was extremely helpful. We also bought a good deal of books together (50-50%).

8. Have you ever used tools supporting the principles of Open Science, FAIR or CARE in your Data Management Plan, such as automated FAIR metrics evaluation tools (FAIR enough, the FAIR evaluator, data management platform, or others)?

I used OPIDOR for the DMP, but nothing else.

9. Have you ever found it difficult to replicate findings obtained by another researcher or to reuse the data that served as the foundation for those conclusions? What was the main reason behind irreproducibility?

This is not applicable to my research.

10. Are you aware of anyone who has attempted to replicate your findings? Was the endeavor a success?

So far no, but we integrate into the MAP database colleagues working on related fields and that's a good experience. We also had an internship (a Master student from Venice) who made a test with the divine names in Homer using our database, designed for inscriptions more than for literary texts. This is stimulating for future avenues of research.

11. According to you, has the institutional mindset around sharing data evolved over time? In particular, how did you find the attitudes of publishers, libraries and policy-makers?

Yes, things are going in the right direction, but slowly and it remains very expensive to publish in open access. Publishers are happy to welcome ERC publications because we are well funded, but for other people this is actually very difficult.

2.3. Andrew Piper

1. Could you describe your research project, which required gathering and disseminating a large amount of data?

I study storytelling in numerous forms with a special focus on contemporary fiction.

2. How do you discover data that is relevant for your research and which factors help you to assess its quality and trustworthiness?

This is a hard question to answer briefly. It is a case by case basis based on domain knowledge. There is no single answer that suffices.

3. What are the scholarly workflows that turn source material into data (extraction, transformation, unifying in a repository, etc.)? How do you develop a shared understanding about data with your collaborators and stakeholders?

Workflow = identification of an ideal data set, collect a sample either manually or in automated fashion (scraping), clean, analyse, clean, then begin processing the data for any subsequent analytical tasks. Again can't be standardised depends on research question on a case by case basis.

4. What is the effect of legal or regulatory limitations on your research design and execution, as well as on your data sharing procedures? What were your relations with data providers and/or copyright holders?

Legal limitations are the single biggest inhibitor to my research. Contemporary publishing has very strong IP protections limiting what researchers can do and study. Imagine having a library where you can't actually use their data! That's our current situation.

5. Do you release your datasets together with your research findings? If yes, in what formats / standards and which repositories? What kind of metadata is used?

Yes. I use Figshare or Dataverse. Data formats depend on the project. Mostly full text data or derived data in tables + metadata.

6. How can you facilitate mutual understanding of each other's data within your discipline? Do you have shared vocabularies, ontologies or metadata standards available?

No standards. Would be good to develop. Though there are standard formats:

- Full text (gold standard rarely achieved)
- Derived data in the form of word frequencies or other features (POS tags etc)
- Metadata that points to a digital library such as the Hathi Trust

7. Have you ever approached a support research agent (such as a data steward, librarian, or archivist) and requested for or received their assistance? Could you name them? How cultural heritage professionals (archivists, librarians, museologists, etc.) can support your work?

No one has ever satisfactorily solved my problems. We do everything ourselves.

8. Have you ever used tools supporting the principles of Open Science, FAIR or CARE in your Data Management Plan, such as automated FAIR metrics evaluation tools (FAIR enough, the FAIR evaluator, data management platform, or others)?

Not currently.

9. Have you ever found it difficult to replicate findings obtained by another researcher or to reuse the data that served as the foundation for those conclusions? What was the main reason behind irreproducibility?

Yes! The main culprit is the unavailability of the data.

10. Are you aware of anyone who has attempted to replicate your findings? Was the endeavor a success?

No not aware.

11. According to you, has the institutional mindset around sharing data evolved over time? In particular, how did you find the attitudes of publishers, libraries and policy-makers?

Improving at a snail's pace.

2.4. Federico Pianzola

1. Could you describe your research project, which required gathering and disseminating a large amount of data?

The “Graphs and Ontologies for Literary Evolution Models” is a 5-year (2023-2027) research project funded by the European Commission (ERC StG). The goal of the project is to create accurate models of how the (formal and content-related) cultural traits of fiction spread and combine. The data used are (fan)fiction stories in 5 different languages (English, Spanish, Italian, Korean, and Indonesian) gathered from various online platforms. The methodology mainly combines computational literary studies and cultural evolution theory, with influences from fan studies and information science.

2. How do you discover data that is relevant for your research and which factors help you to assess its quality and trustworthiness?

Discovery: Google Scholar alerts for topics of interest; following researchers on social media; checking data journals and repositories (OSF, CESSDA, Zenodo, Journal of Open Humanities Data) ; Assessment: I look at the documentation and try to understand how the data has been collected, annotated, transformed. I always double-check the methodology to make sure I agree with the modelling decisions made by others.

3. What are the scholarly workflows that turn source material into data (extraction, transformation, unifying in a repository, etc.)? How do you develop a shared understanding about data with your collaborators and stakeholders?

Workflow: discussion of theory and data modelling (e.g. taxonomies, psychological constructs, ontologies); extraction; transformation; enrichment using annotation; organisation based on standards, ontologies, and vocabularies; unifying in a repository.

4. What is the effect of legal or regulatory limitations on your research design and execution, as well as on your data sharing procedures? What were your relations with data providers and/or copyright holders?

Often I can't share data because it is copyrighted. I've recently started sharing derived data and enriched metadata. I always inform data providers and online users when I'm using their data for research. In the case of large scale collection, I contact the website administrators and/or post an announcement on their websites.

5. Do you release your datasets together with your research findings? If yes, in what formats / standards and which repositories? What kind of metadata is used?

Yes. Always open formats: e.g. CSV. Metadata about the content, original source, creator, date, disciplines of interest.

6. How can you facilitate mutual understanding of each other's data within your discipline? Do you have shared vocabularies, ontologies or metadata standards available?

Making explicit and documenting all data modelling choices. Available ontologies don't cover all aspects of research data in CLS, e.g. there is a big gap related to narrative and fictional elements. It's important to start using more frequently existing ontologies: CIDOC-CRM, NLP Interchange Format, OntoLex, etc.

7. Have you ever approached a support research agent (such as a data steward, librarian, or archivist) and requested for or received their assistance? Could you name them? How cultural heritage professionals (archivists, librarians, museologists, etc.) can support your work?

Yes, at my own institution (University of Groningen). They can help in: - making data collection more comprehensive and accurate - clarify legal and ethical issues - support in documentation and sharing data

8. Have you ever used tools supporting the principles of Open Science, FAIR or CARE in your Data Management Plan, such as automated FAIR metrics evaluation tools (FAIR enough, the FAIR evaluator, data management platform, or others)?

Yes. OSF, Data Stewardship Wizard.

9. Have you ever found it difficult to replicate findings obtained by another researcher or to reuse the data that served as the foundation for those conclusions? What was the main reason behind irreproducibility?

Yes. Lack of clear documentation and commented code.

10. Are you aware of anyone who has attempted to replicate your findings? Was the endeavor a success?

Yes, I know of an ongoing attempt but they're having troubles because we can't share copyrighted data.

11. According to you, has the institutional mindset around sharing data evolved over time? In particular, how did you find the attitudes of publishers, libraries and policy-makers?

Only slightly changed in the humanities. Many scholars are still not aware of the importance of sharing data. I'm very happy that the EU is pushing hard their Open Science agenda, forcing others to adapt to it.

2.5. Maciej Eder

1. Could you describe your research project, which required gathering and disseminating a large amount of data?

Our research projects at the Institute for Polish Language of the Polish Academy of Sciences focus on applying computational techniques to analyze texts. While these texts could be generally considered to be literary, some non-literary sources (or even non-textual in the strictest sense) also fall into our area of interest. The goal of most of these projects is to uncover patterns, themes, and similarities across texts using methods such as clustering, topic modeling, and sentiment analysis. The actual size of the datasets might vary. Some of the projects conducted by our team include:

- a series of studies on language change (<https://computationalstylistics.github.io/projects/chronology/>) that required a few relatively large diachronic corpora of Polish and English
- a PhD project on Multimodal stylometry, in which tons of TV series are being downloaded and statistically analyzed
- a PhD project on Latin poetry (<https://computationalstylistics.github.io/projects/latin-poetry/>) that relies on a relatively small but very well-curated collection of Latin poems
- a project on automatic detection of direct speech in literary corpora in several languages (https://computationalstylistics.github.io/projects/direct_speech/) relying mostly on the high-quality corpus ELTeC containing 1200+ novels in several languages
- a series of methodological studies aimed at testing different stylometric methods (<https://computationalstylistics.github.io/projects/methodology/>), for which a series of comparable corpora in a few languages – each containing a few dozen full-sized novels out of copyright – had to be collected.

2. How do you discover data that is relevant for your research and which factors help you to assess its quality and trustworthiness?

Discovering relevant data involves a combination of methods such as literature review, online databases, digital libraries, and collaborations with other researchers or institutions that specialise in digitising and archiving literary materials. Factors that help assess data quality and trustworthiness include: 1. accuracy (controlling the amount of errors of different type), 2. completeness (obvious, but not always easy to meet), 3. metadata (met rather rarely, or at most at an elementary level), 4. source reputation, 5. consistency (of a paramount importance when a larger corpus acquired from several sources is concerned), 6. validation (ideal data), 7. permissions & copyrights (a problematic topic, of course). By considering the above factors, one can make informed decisions about which

data sources to utilise for further research. From the above list of factors, certainly #5 (source reputation) is decisive. In our team, we rely on established collections of literary texts, such as the Gutenberg Project, ELTeC, DraCor, Bibliotheca Augustana, The Latin Library, Perseus Project, and the like initiatives.

3. What are the scholarly workflows that turn source material into data (extraction, transformation, unifying in a repository, etc.)? How do you develop a shared understanding about data with your collaborators and stakeholders?

Scholarly workflows for turning source material into data typically involve several stages: 1. data acquisition, as discussed above, 2. data extraction in a broad sense (including digitizing from paper copies or extracting raw text data from different formats such as PDFs, HTML, etc.), 3. data preprocessing, which usually means cleaning obvious errors, removing noise and formatting inconsistencies, improving metadata; 4. normalization, by which one can understand both standardising spellings and/or modernising, to ensure consistency across the dataset; 5. structural annotation if necessary, 6. grammatical annotation, or applying a set of NLP procedures in order to add information about grammatical categories (parts of speech), named entity recognition, etc., 7. repository integration: usually putting a dataset on GitHub and/or our Institute's GitLab instance.

To develop a shared understanding about the data with collaborators and stakeholders, communication and documentation are essential. These include:

- Collaborative meetings: regular meetings or discussions (in-person or hybrid) where team members can share their progress, insights, and challenges related to the data.
- Documentation: creating detailed documentation that outlines the data collection methods, preprocessing steps, metadata format, and any assumptions or limitations associated with the dataset. These are all of paramount importance, but in practice, we adopted a rule-of-thumb saying that at least some basic documentation should always be provided.
- Data samples: ideally, some data excerpts should be made available even for copyrighted materials, in order to illustrate the characteristics and potential insights of the dataset. In practice, since sharing the full-text datasets is restricted, we adopted a routine of sharing derived data on GitHub, such as word frequencies instead of original texts.
- Feedback: establishing any feedback mechanism where collaborators can provide input, suggestions, or corrections to improve the quality and usability of the data. In our case, such feedback mechanism is mostly informal, via casual chats between team members.
- Training and workshops: Providing training sessions or workshops to familiarize collaborators with the data, analytical tools, and methods used in the research project.

By fostering open communication and collaboration, researchers can develop a shared understanding of the data and ensure alignment among stakeholders throughout the research process.

4. What is the effect of legal or regulatory limitations on your research design and execution, as well as on your data sharing procedures? What were your relations with data providers and/or copyright holders?

Legal and regulatory limitations can significantly impact research design, execution, and data sharing procedures in computational text analysis of literary materials. In particular, in the area of Computational Literary Studies researchers would be very much interested in analyzing massive amounts of contemporary literature. For copyright reasons, however, this is very rarely possible, and this puts computational approaches to literature in a less comfortable position in comparison to traditional literary studies. Let's face it: contemporary literature is and has always been the most vibrant topic in literary studies. In a way similar, however, is the situation of Ancient texts (say, Latin and Greek), as well as Early Modern ones. In order to acquire a reasonable dataset a researcher has to rely on outdated 19th-century editions that are freely accessible on Gutenberg Project and the like repositories. Using any state-of-the-art critical edition of Ancient or Medieval text might be virtually impossible due to the copyright reasons. Exceptions include The Riddle of Literary Quality project conducted at Huygens Institute (KNAW) in Amsterdam. On special permission from the publishers, the team of that project could use the original full-size contemporary novels, provided that all the books were accessed remotely using API queries. Consequently, the researchers did not see the books themselves, they were however allowed to conduct (remotely) any analysis they wished.

5. Do you release your datasets together with your research findings? If yes, in what formats / standards and which repositories? What kind of metadata is used?

Yes, releasing datasets alongside research findings has become a common practice in computational text analysis research; our team is no exception. The choice of formats, standards, and repositories for data sharing depends on the specific requirements of the research community and the preferences of the researchers. Obviously, however, TEI is a standard (or format) that first comes to mind. In several other applications raw text files can be processed directly, so the actual format is TXT. When grammatical annotation is concerned, we either comply with TEI, or the so-called vertical format, which is a combination of simple markup and formatting the text in three columns; the columns contain, in each row, a subsequent word form (as it appears in the text), its recognized lemma, followed by a part-of-speech tag.

Metadata accompanying the datasets varies, and depends on the purpose the dataset had been created. Bare minimum is to provide, for each text in a corpus, its author and title, and preferably also a publication year. In a more ideal scenario, which we try to comply with but rarely have sufficient resources to efficiently do so, it includes information such as:

- Title
- Author(s) or creator(s)
- Date of creation or publication
- Gender of the author

- Genre of a literary work
- License or terms of use
- Data format and encoding
- Source(s) of the data
- Any preprocessing steps applied to the data
- Relevant identifiers (e.g. DOI)
- Keywords

By providing comprehensive metadata, researchers enable others to understand, evaluate, and effectively reuse the datasets for further analysis or validation. Adhering to community standards and best practices for data sharing facilitates collaboration, reproducibility, and the advancement of knowledge in computational text analysis and digital humanities.

6. How can you facilitate mutual understanding of each other's data within your discipline? Do you have shared vocabularies, ontologies or metadata standards available?

Facilitating mutual understanding of data within the discipline of computational text analysis and digital humanities involves several strategies, including the use of shared vocabularies, ontologies, and metadata standards. In practice, however, our team has rather little to share in terms of, say, metadata standards. Rather than sharing our solution, we put as much effort as possible to comply with the already existing standards and shared vocabularies. An exception rather than a rule is our way to embed metadata about literary works in the filenames of the respective text files. Several years ago, for the purpose of conducting methodological experiments in authorship attribution, a simple way of using filenames to avoid any additional tables containing metadata was used, e.g. the file "austen_pride.txt" suggests to contain the novel "Pride and Prejudice" by Jane Austen. This simple way was first used in the stylometric software 'stylo' and received a reasonable acceptance in the area of CLS studies (or even more broadly).

7. Have you ever approached a support research agent (such as a data steward, librarian, or archivist) and requested for or received their assistance? Could you name them? How cultural heritage professionals (archivists, librarians, museologists, etc.) can support your work?

It is easy to say that collaboration with cultural heritage professionals enables researchers to leverage their expertise and resources to enhance the quality, accessibility, and impact of their work in computational text analysis and digital humanities. It's more difficult to achieve, though. Direct example of such collaboration includes our project on the language change in Polish, for which we had to acquire a possibly large corpus of texts covering a few centuries. A big help was offered by the foundation "Wolne Lektury": not only were we allowed to download their content, but they also consulted with us which 19th-century texts should be digitized first. A similar attitude towards digitizing resources in communication with potential users or stakeholders is presented by the librarians from the Polish National Library working on the collection Polona.

8. Have you ever used tools supporting the principles of Open Science, FAIR or CARE in your Data Management Plan, such as automated FAIR metrics evaluation tools (FAIR enough, the FAIR evaluator, data management platform, or others)?

Not really. While there is awareness of their existence in our team, we rarely (if at all) incorporate them into our research workflows. In the context of the project conducted by our team, the FAIR principles are relatively easy to keep an eye on (certainly, in the cases when the source materials are not copyrighted or not possible to turn into FAIR data for other external reasons). In such a case, any additional tooling is not really helpful. The tools, however, that indirectly contribute to keeping our datasets FAIR, is a set of open-source technologies we adopted at the Institute. These include a version control system GitHub that enables researchers to manage changes to their datasets and track the evolution of data over time. We routinely deposit our code and datasets either on GitLab, or on GitHub. By doing this, we hope to promote transparency, reproducibility, and collaboration, which certainly aligns with the principles of FAIR, Open Science, and CARE (Collective Benefit).

9. Have you ever found it difficult to replicate findings obtained by another researcher or to reuse the data that served as the foundation for those conclusions? What was the main reason behind irreproducibility?

Many times it happened; more often than not. I could even say that replication is routinely an issue, for different reasons, ranging from the so-called software dependencies (e.g. some Python libraries cannot be installed in older versions), to the code that contains very specific settings (e.g. absolute paths to the data, which by definition looks different on different machines). Some common reasons behind irreproducibility include:

- Insufficient documentation of data sources, preprocessing steps, analysis procedures, and software dependencies makes it difficult for other researchers to understand and replicate the research workflow. Lack of detailed documentation hinders reproducibility by obscuring key decisions and assumptions made during the research process.
- Poor data quality, including errors, inconsistencies, and biases in the dataset, can lead to irreproducibility of findings.
- Software dependencies: dependency on specific software tools, libraries, or platforms that are not well-documented, maintained, or accessible to other researchers can hinder reproducibility. Changes in software versions, compatibility issues, or lack of access to proprietary tools may prevent researchers from replicating analyses or reusing code.
- Limited access to the original data sources or restrictions on data sharing due to privacy concerns, copyright issues, or licensing agreements can impede reproducibility. Without access to the underlying data, researchers cannot independently verify the findings or conduct alternative analyses.
- Lack of transparency in reporting analytical methods, parameter settings, and decision criteria makes it challenging for other researchers to reproduce the results. Ambiguities in methodological descriptions, such as vague or incomplete descriptions of algorithms or statistical procedures, undermine reproducibility by introducing uncertainty into the research process.

- Last but not least, irreproducibility may also result from human factors such as errors in data processing, coding, or interpretation, as well as differences in researcher expertise, experience, or domain knowledge.

Without clear documentation and standardized procedures, variations in human judgment and interpretation can lead to inconsistencies in replication attempts. Addressing these challenges requires concerted efforts to promote transparency, rigor, and openness in computational text analysis and digital humanities research. Emphasizing comprehensive documentation, data validation, open access to data and code, methodological transparency, and community standards can enhance reproducibility and facilitate the reuse of research findings by other scholars.

10. Are you aware of anyone who has attempted to replicate your findings? Was the endeavor a success?

Well, yes and no. Yes because there have been a few studies aimed at using my code and/or my dataset to repeat my analytical steps. And no, because these experiments are not replication studies in the strict sense. Usual practice is to take someone else's code, and to apply it to an extended dataset, in order to confirm the validity of the original findings. Or, sometimes a different programming language is used to replicate an original analytical procedure (e.g. preprocessing) in order to use it in a more general setup.

As far as my experience suggests, replication in the sciences is an idea rather than an actual scholarly routine. An idea, because the code and the datasets should be made publicly available in order to make a study in question entirely replicable. In practice, however, it is much more beneficial for the sake of advancing human knowledge if a study in question opens a new perspective, and paves a way to replicate the original study in slightly different conditions. It is more beneficial, in my opinion, to extend the original study by new languages, new genres, or new literary periods. (Let alone the fact that an ideal replication study would be very difficult to publish).

11. According to you, has the institutional mindset around sharing data evolved over time? In particular, how did you find the attitudes of publishers, libraries and policy-makers?

Yes it did evolve, for sure. My own observations over the last 20 years or so definitely confirm that such an evolving attitude cannot be denied. The institutional mindset around sharing data has evolved over time, driven by various factors such as technological advancements, changes in scholarly communication practices, and shifting cultural norms regarding openness and transparency in research. Here's how attitudes of publishers, libraries, and policy-makers have evolved:

- Publishers: many publishers have increasingly embraced open access and data sharing initiatives in response to growing demands for transparency and reproducibility in research. Some publishers now require authors to provide access to underlying data as a condition for publication, and they may offer data repositories or supplemental materials hosting options to facilitate data sharing. Additionally, publishers are implementing policies to promote data citation and encourage proper attribution of shared datasets, recognizing the value of data as a scholarly output.

- Libraries play a pivotal role in supporting data sharing and management efforts within the research community. They provide infrastructure, services, and expertise to help researchers organize, preserve, and disseminate their data effectively. Libraries may offer data management planning support, data repository services, data curation assistance, and training programs to promote best practices in data sharing and stewardship. Moreover, libraries advocate for open access principles and collaborate with publishers, researchers, and policymakers to advance open science initiatives and facilitate broader access to research outputs, including data.

- Policy-makers at various levels, including funding agencies, government, and international organizations, have recognized the importance of data sharing for accelerating scientific discovery, fostering innovation, and maximizing the societal impact of research investments. As a result, many funding agencies (such as the Polish agency NCN) have implemented data sharing requirements as part of grant conditions, mandating researchers to deposit their data in repositories, adhere to data management plans, and make data publicly accessible. Additionally, policy-makers are promoting open science policies and infrastructure development to enhance data discoverability, accessibility, and reuse across disciplines and borders. Overall, there has been a noticeable shift towards greater support for data sharing and open science principles among publishers, libraries, and policy-makers. While challenges remain, such as ensuring data privacy and addressing concerns about intellectual property rights, the growing emphasis on transparency, collaboration, and knowledge exchange is driving positive change in research culture and practices.

3. Research Good Practices, FAIR Data and Research Data Life Cycle

Author: Carolin Odebrecht

The **FAIR Guiding Principles** (Wilkinson et al. 2016) state that (meta)data should be Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable. FAIR represents the interface between the high-level goals of **research integrity** and **openness** on the one hand and the process model **research data life cycle**, on the other, developed within the context of **research data management**. This wiki section will explain the connections between the values and the practices as well as provide examples from the CLS domain of addressing both kinds of issues.

[FAIR Guiding Principles](#)

The FAIR Guiding Principles provide a clear goal for data (and software) which refers directly to our good scientific practices providing the fundament of **research integrity**: "Research integrity is crucial to preserving the trustworthiness of the research system and its results." (ALLEA 2023).

FAIR data can be interpreted as the overarching goal of **research data management**: "Research data management is an explicit process covering the creation and stewardship of research materials to enable their use for as long as they retain value" (DCC digital curation glossary, entry "[Research Data Management](#)"). **Research data life cycle** is an established model of how research data

management should be implemented: it is a process model that sets main steps of data handling in a temporal and / or functional relation (Cox and Tan 2018).

Take-home message: The FAIR Guiding principles specify the high-level goals of research integrity and openness by relating them to the domain of (meta)data, for which the research data life cycle provides an implementation process model.

Research Data Life Cycle

The research data life cycle model focuses on the main tasks of data handling that pertain to the entirety of the research process. Thus, it relates the **general goals** of attaining FAIR data to **concrete tasks**, which researchers confront when implementing their individual schemes.

Typically, the research process starts with planning and designing that establishes the goals and parameters of corpus design, data management, and research questions and methods alongside devising a strategy for the publication of research results and data (Section 3.1). These decisions serve as a blueprint for data collection and / or creation (Section 3.2), followed by data preparation and enrichment (Section 3.3). The analysis stage is closely connected to and evaluated with a view to the research goals (Section 3.4). For a sustainable conclusion of the research, it is also necessary to back up, document, and publish all the data generated in the process (Section 3.5). References to software and applications that are necessary to address each step should be considered as well. Finally, published data becomes a subject of reuse practices (Section 3.6).

Take-home message: The research data life cycle provides a blueprint for planning and implementing a research (data) project in keeping with the FAIR Guiding Principles and the values of the openness and reproducibility of research results.

Connection of CLS data to FAIR, Research Integrity, and Research Data Life Cycle

Connecting these abstract goals, models, and guidelines to concrete research situations presents a major challenge both for researchers and institutions, in whose broader context the former operate. In **the context of CLS**, these challenges can be broken down into three fundamental questions:

- How can planning and design effectively address CLS-specific requirements?
- Which CLS-specific parameters for data are needed to be considered during implementation?
- Which publication strategies enable the research community to reuse CLS data according to the FAIR Guiding Principles?

In order to address these questions and to foster adaptability and knowledge transfer, we provide this wiki with CLS examples for each step of the research data life cycle. In addition, disciplines typically develop domain-specific requirements concerning such overarching notions as **accessibility or interoperability**. “Accessibility” may refer to human interaction with data (searching for data using meta-search engines) or to machine-accessible interfaces that enable automatic data crawling. For “Interoperability”, domain-specific best practices in selecting formats, schemas, and applications need to be considered (and **documented**).

Take-home message: The implementation of the FAIR Guiding Principles requires an application of meta-requirements that pertain to all disciplines working with digital data to unique research projects. This application process requires **interpretation** in this sense that domain-specific characteristics of data, research procedures, and output need to be defined and implemented in each step of the research data life cycle.

Documentation

Documentation is a method that explicitly protocols the steps of the research data life cycle and and the measures for compliance with good scientific practice. Documentation is therefore connected to every Section in this wiki and can be implemented in several forms connected to the documentation goal and addresses, e.g.:

- Data handbook
- Data management plan
- Data collection protocol
- Metadata
- README

3.1. Planning and Designing Data

Author: Carolin Odebrecht

Firstly, CLS data typically require a careful **corpus design** reflecting for example the preservation conditions of sources and their genre [see CLS INFRA's Survey of Methods](#), (Schöch et al. 2023) and register (Biber 2019) identification, authorship attribution (Schöch et al. 2023), and the evaluation or classification of textual material with regard to, e.g., cultural, social, and literary contexts, traditions, and canonicity in specific CLS domains. In this section, we present three types of corpus design: [Designed Corpus](#), [Opportunistic/Growing/Dynamic Corpus](#) and [Edition](#).

Secondly, designing the ways of the **preparation** and especially the **annotation** of CLS data appears to be particularly demanding (Section 3.3).

Thirdly, the **availability** of resources and their **terms of use** must be clarified at the initial stage of planning and designing (Section 3.5).

CLS data in general requires an intensive corpus design including but not limited to:

- eligibility: definition of the CLS data that is the research object
- scope: parameters which refer either to literature itself (corpus-internal) or to contextual information not directly connected to the literature (corpus-external)
- amount, proportion and sampling: parameters defining the amount and the composition of a data collection with regard to the design parameters and metadata
- metadata: often interrelated to the corpus design parameter
- domain-adaptability: reflection about representativeness, bias, and canonicity

These design criteria operationalise the decision made by the corpus creators in relation to the corpus-internal and corpus-external aspects of the literary data, e.g., authorship, work, genre, period, bibliographical metadata, publication history and availability, text length and language.

3.1.1. Designed corpus

European Literary Text Collection ([ELTeC](#), cf. Odebrecht and Biskup 2021) can serve as an example of a careful corpus design in the domain of CLS and is one of the key deliverables of the COST Action 'Distant Reading for European Literary History' (CA16204). ELTeC is a designed collection of literary texts and serves as a benchmark corpus for computational methods in CLS. "Its composition is determined not by the happenstance of whatever we can get our hands on, but is instead defensible, at least in theory, as a principled and representative selection." (Burnard et al. 2021).

- eligibility: narrative text of a minimum length, written in languages that are used in Europe, no translations

- scope: 100 texts per language
- proportion and sampling: min/max proportion regarding author gender, text length, year of origin, reprint count
- metadata: bibliographical metadata and references to full bibliographic entries provided by libraries and [GND/VIAF](#), proportion criteria parameter, word count, data editors, project, version
- domain-adaptability: research focusing on (European) narrative prose, CLS in a broad sense

This corpus design focuses on a metadata-based approach that reflects potential novel candidates but does not determine in advance what a novel in a European literary perspective might be. Furthermore, as the population of European novels cannot be defined (yet), i.e. no extensive bibliography of the European novel exists, the corpus design focuses on the representation of variation and not of the population.

For collaborative projects and large data sets, corpus monitoring might be applicable. ELTeC is monitored on the base of each text's metadata: [ELTeC-Monitoring](#).

The collection of [Eighteenth-Century French Novels](#) is another good example for a designed corpus that uses balancing criteria (Röttgermann 2023). "The collection is created in the context of Mining and Modeling Text (2019-2023), a project which is located at the Trier Center for Digital Humanities (TCDH) at Trier University." (cf. [Homepage](#)).

- eligibility: 18th century French novels
- scope: bibliography documenting the overall production of novels in the period is Angus Martin, Vivienne G. Mylne and Richard Frautschi, *Bibliographie du genre romanesque français 1751-1800*, 1977 (BGRF)
- amount, proportion and sampling: parameters gender, year of first publication and narrative form
- metadata: bibliographical metadata, based on BGRF
- domain-adaptability: known historical publication proportions of the French novel according to BGRF

This collection enables researchers to design their corpora by referring to a documented population (BGRF). As a result, they can model the corpus's balancing criteria with reference to the population.

For collaborative projects and large data sets, corpus monitoring may be applicable. This collection is monitored on the base of each text's metadata: [Eighteen-Century French Novel-Monitoring](#).

3.1.2. Opportunistic / Growing / Dynamic Corpus

The Drama Corpora Project ([DraCor](#), cf. Fischer et al. 2019) contains an ever-growing collection of plays in (mostly) European languages and provides an Open Access platform for displaying, analysing, and downloading drama data. The corpus design focuses on the genre drama without any pre-determined sub-genre or/and subject classifications that could shape the corpus composition.

- eligibility: any open access text that is associated as a drama and is written in an European language, no translations
- scope: no definition of scope to be reached
- amount, proportion and sampling: data collection are grouped by language, no other criteria are used for composition and collection
- metadata: bibliographic metadata that reflect date of origin, authorship, language, and source
- domain-adaptability: drama as a canonical genre, bias by opportunistic approach to, for example, the number of dramas in a given language

Growing corpora have the advantage over the scoped ones that new data can be added continuously without having to check for, e.g., balance or composition criteria. DraCor lays the foundation for research projects that are for instance compiling data from different sources to a designed corpus or that focus genre-specific research in either mono- or multilingual settings.

The Diachronic Spanish Sonnet Corpus ([DISCO](#), cf Ruiz Fabo and Sabel 2023) is another example of a growing corpus that focuses on sonnets in Spanish from 15th to early-mid 20th century.

- eligibility: Spanish poems that are identified as canonical and non-canonical sonnets
- scope: no definition of scope to be reached
- proportion and sampling: no strict criteria, monitoring of the corpus composition by metadata
- metadata: bibliographical metadata, references to [VIAF](#), references to sources
- domain-adaptability: research focusing on Spanish sonnets (world wide)

With the help of a corpus monitoring, the composition of the corpus can be explored. For example, it is stated that "Although overall in the corpus we deliberately included less canonical writers, less than 10% of the authors are female. An active search will be carried out to counteract this lack of diversity." [DISCO Corpus monitoring](#)

3.1.3. Digital Edition

The [Faust-Edition](#) (Bohnenkamp et al.) is an example for a digital edition. It collects and presents the manuscripts and the text-critically relevant printings of *Faust* that were published during Goethe's lifetime in order to make the analysis of the work's genesis possible. Central for this digital edition is that the textual variants can be analysed individually, in the context of others variants, and the entire genesis of the work.

- eligibility: every piece of text which is a variant of the work *Faust* and is written by Goethe
- scope: the lifetime of the author
- amount, proportion and sampling: everything that is preserved in an archive or collection
- metadata: bibliographic metadata
- domain-adaptability: research on the drama *Faust*, methodical research on digital editions, multitextual visualisation and analysis

3.2. Creation and Collection of Data

Author: Michał Mrugalski

3.2.1. The Notion of Data and their Collection / Creation

Nothing else has the same impact on research findings in CLS as collecting / creating data according to a corpus design (On Corpus Design see section 3.1). At this stage, researchers can control a wide range of variables as their manipulation of these variables ultimately result in varied outcomes.

Conducive to the openness and the reproducibility of research, it is recommend that CLS researchers from the outset regard the process of collecting and creating data (corpora) as producing an **artifact that can be reused by other researchers** (Harrower et al. 2020: 9).

But why the slash symbol between “**collecting**” and “**creating**” data? Why the insistence that “data” in CLS is a function of a “corpus” design?

To quote a well-received essay collection, “raw data is an oxymoron” (Gitelman 2013). The process of “collecting” data is not “harvesting” “raw” material, but in fact always happens with a view to an envisioned corpus; a corpus design predetermines what one looks for. “Data” is something that exists in a corpus and only as a function of a corpus can be an object of study in the framework of CLS. And the other way round: the creation of a CLS dataset inevitably entails reusing pre-existing data.

The first step in any CLS research project amounts thus to **explicitly defining** what one understands as “data”, especially since Literary Studies abstains from using the very term. As Jennifer Edmond and Erzsébet Tóth-Czifra put it, literary scholars “resist the blanket term ‘data’ for the very good reason that we have more and precise terminology (e.g. primary sources, secondary sources, theoretical documents, bibliographies, critical editions, annotations, notes, etc.) available to us to describe and make transparent our research processes” (Edmond and Tóth-Czifra 2018: 1).

But since in computer science, “**data**” is a pendant of “**computing**”, it is hard to imagine CLS without a notion of data; not to mention that a good portion of CLS research consists of applying the procedures of “data science” to corpora of literary texts. Of course, these procedures are adapted to issues of interest for literary or cultural scholars, such as narrative point of view (Piper and Bagga 2022; Piper and Toubia 2023).

The authors of the Allea group report (Harrower et al. 2020: 8) propose to define “data in the humanities broadly as all materials and assets scholars collect, generate and use during all stages of the research cycle.” Some of these data have “digital form” and as such they are the object of CLS. By “**digital**” we mean their quality of being machine manipulable, i.e. primarily countable and enrichable (they can be annotated or commented on, see 3.3). As discreet, they can also easily be subjected to reduction, as with the removal of stop words, etc.

With reproducibility in mind and in keeping with the FAIR principles, we cannot think of data in isolation from an **identifier** and **metadata**, which both allow for the identification of the data set, its

provenance alongside the enrichments the data went through in the process of collection / creation and subsequent pre-processing as well as analysis. The authors of the Allea group report (Harrower et al. 2020: 17) deem it “central to the realization of FAIR” that we use “the concept of a FAIR digital object – an elemental ‘bundle’ that includes the research data, the persistent identifier (PID), and “metadata rich enough to enable them to be reliably found, used and cited.” In short, our research corpus is a **bundle** consisting of data, PID, and metadata.

The explicit definition of (our) data should be made part of a **protocol of data collection / creation**. A central aspect of a reproducibility-centered open-science-mindedness is **documenting the process of data collection and creation**, in the form of a protocol, where a researcher describes how they obtained each piece of data (Desquilbet et al. 2019: 53, see also 32). The protocol should contain maximum information as “at the beginning of a project it is difficult to judge which information of the research process will be important and valuable later on” (Harrower et al. 2020: 9) and to other researchers. Qualities of research objects change when you change the method of observation, therefore both your harvesting method and your protocol should be as standardized as possible (Desquilbet et al. 2019: 25-26).

Ideally, the information contained in the collection protocol should be part of the published article reporting the results of your research (Desquilbet et al. 2019: 53). In the case of CLS, it may mean that one documents the process of data collection and creation with the intention of publishing a **data paper**, either in a public repository or in a **journal dedicated to the publication of open data**. A list of such journals include (cf. Tóth-Czifra et al. 2023: 76):

- [Research Data Journal for the Humanities and Social Sciences](#)
- [Journal of Open Humanities Data](#)
- [Journal of Cultural Analytics](#)
- [Journal of the Text Encoding Initiative](#)
- [RIDE – A Review Journal for Digital Editions and Resources](#)

[Die Zeitschrift für digitale Geisteswissenschaften](#) likewise welcomes data publications. Some of those journals, particularly the *Journal of Open Humanities Data*, publish [templates](#) for the assessment of corpora. The criteria contained in said templates can serve researchers as a guide, when rendering their own corpora and their own protocols of rendering corpora.

Take-home message: in the spirit of FAIR-ness, researchers should explicitly define their data with the view to their corpus design and research intention and log all collecting decisions, ideally with a view to publishing not only their data, but also a data paper expanding on a rationale for their choices.

3.2.2. Creating Data by Collecting them in Corpora

The object of study in CLS is not a single text, but a collection of text or a corpus (Gavin 2022: chapter 1): The slash between creation and collection means that CLS researchers basically **create data by collecting textual materials according to their general corpus design**.

As discussed in 3.1, **eligibility** of texts and the texts' **relations to one another** within the corpus provide an additional order turning textual noise into data, loaded with potential information for analysis to extract. Should the corpus consist of whole "works" or just their fragments, and, if the latter holds, how to state the limit of textual pieces? (Most computational methods tokenize texts, turning them into "bags of words", so, in contradistinction to traditional literary analysis, the analysis of segments of comparable length renders more reliable results than one based on "entire" utterances.) How to get hold of textual material? Can it be found online in a more or less reliable source or should it be digitized? How? By applying Optical Character Recognition or by manually typing in words? How should the OCR process or typing be verified?

Unless we create our data from scratch, the recommended sources for CLS include **general-purpose collections** (see our deliverable D5.1), such as HathiTrust Digital Library or Wikisource, data published by researchers in the framework of specific research projects in **trusted repositories** and perhaps even reviewed in data journals. Trusted repositories for CLS include, alongside GitHub and GitLab pages associated with specific research projects,

- [Zenodo](#)
- [Dataverse](#)
- [Figshare](#)
- [SND](#)
- [DANS](#)
- [D-Space](#)

A good starting point is a registry of Research Data Repositories, such as <https://www.re3data.org/> or [FAIRsharing.org](https://fairsharing.org), [Humanities Commons](#), [UK Data Archive](#), [Arche](#). "While browsing humanities datasets, one should take into account whether one's own dataset "could be published in a similar fashion" (Harrower et al. 2020: 9).

One important source of data in the humanities are GLAM institutions (galleries, libraries, archives, museums). To ensure a smooth cooperation with GLAM institutions, it is advised to rely on a set of guidelines, which include models for specific agreements between institutions and researchers, such as [Appendix1 to The Heritage Data Reuse Charter](#). [The Heritage Data Reuse Charter](#) is an implementation in the context of the arts and humanities of the [DARIAH Campus Reuse Charter](#). You can find out more about data reuse in section 3.6.

Texts must be **encoded** in a particular way (modelling resp. encoding scheme and **format**), that allows for annotation and manipulation. As for **data and encoding formats**, it is recommended to utilize open-license (non-proprietary) formats curated by the World Wide Web Consortium W3C (mostly XLM, RDF, JSON), especially as they undergo enrichment and concretization under the

auspices of international communities, such as [Text Encoding Initiative \(TEI\)](#), [Music Encoding Initiative \(MEI\)](#), and [International Image Interoperability Framework \(IIIF\)](#). Moreover, human and machine-readable systems are preferable to only machine-readable ones as it “provides better sustainability and long-term accessibility” (Harrower et al. 2020: 20).

Metadata captures exactly information on the eligibility, provenance, format, and modelling of the data. Consistent with the FAIR principles, your metadata should adopt one of the common standards, e.g. [Dublin Core](#), [MARC](#) (a library cataloging standard), or an archive standard [EAD](#) (Harrower et al. 2020: 17) “A good starting point is to consult the [Metadata Standards Directory](#), a community-maintained directory hosted by the Research Data Alliance” (Harrower et al. 2020: 18).

In some encoding formats, such as XML/TEI metadata make part of a document; in other cases, they are usually contained in separate file, for example as a csv table or a json “dictionary”.

It is important to rely on a controlled vocabulary for choosing your metadata categories. In literary studies, there is no one universally accepted standard as you may see it in the interviews with our experts. The most popular standards FRBROO and CIDOC CRM are very high-level and it is up to literary researchers to specify them with regard to literary terms. A literary particularization was implemented in an exemplary way in the [POSTDATA Network of Ontologies for European Poetry](#). One can rely on the Library of Congress for subject headings or make use of the catalog of vocabularies (especially Art and Architecture (Getty)) or, even better, wikidata, because of wikibase’s great potential to create a basis for knowledge graphs that inscribe our output into the Linked Open Data universe.

To “clean” your metadata, think about utilizing an application like [Open Refine](#).

Take-home message: Researchers create textual data by collecting them for the sake of their corpus design that determines the scope, balance, provenance, format, and encoding of meta-data. Of course, all decisions should be documented in a data collection protocol.

3.3. Preparation and Enrichment of Data

Author: Michał Mrugalski

3.3.1 Pre-processing Data

Data preparation and enrichment cannot be easily separated from the following step in the life cycle of data, data analysis (discussed in [3.4](#)). Since data processing is typically **the first step of data analysis**, the way in which we approach a corpus with a research question and hypothesis will determine how the data is prepared. In CLS, these preparation processes typically involve

- digitalization (via OCR or manual transcription) of printed texts or / and re-appropriation of digital electronic material (see [3.6](#))

- layout analysis including e.g. removing noise or unwanted text (editor's footnotes, running head, etc.)
- segmenting text on a sub-sentence level (tokenization, stemming, lemmatization)
- removing so-called stop-words (mostly when we are interested in semantic analysis such as such as Topication, Sentiment Analysis, Named Entity Recognition, see 3.4)
- annotating text

Texts can be annotated both on the

- document level (metadata) and
- token level (tagging)

(based on: <https://methods.clsinfra.io/annotation-intro.html>). Standard operations on textual data require all or at least most of these steps as prerequisites.

Take-home message: The preparation of data is the first step of data analysis. Data and metadata are best prepared simultaneously: annotation processes on the document level notwithstanding, it is important to create metadata that describes data as soon as possible since metadata should contain information on pre-processing. The preparation of (meta)data is done with an explicit vision of the research outcome and research method in mind, as stated in **the data collection protocol**, and should likewise be **documented** in a log (see section 3.2).

3.3.2. Improving Quality of Data

The preparation of data in a broader sense, by no means limited to CLS or NLP, pertains to the **quality of data** that is intended to undergo an analysis. In this case, preparation amounts to **data enrichment** understood as “the process of enhancing existing information by

- supplementing missing or incomplete data” (Allen and Cervo 2015: 152) and / or
- enhancing “collected data with relevant context obtained from additional sources” (Knapp and Langill 2015: 343).

This usually occurs by adding new attributes, like for example supplementing a wikitext with literary historical metadata or comparing it with a standard edition. Problems with data quality have various root reasons, some related to data in general and some particular to CLS.

Duplicate data is a broad term for problems that arise when the same data, though somewhat different, is entered more than once when extracting data from several sources (e.g., libraries or general collections). In particular, **duplicate data** for CLS may indicate a lack of knowledge of literary history: for instance, the same poem or narrative prose appears twice in a corpus due to variations in author attribution, title, or even name spelling. Older literature is typically far less standardized in paratextual terms. This could be addressed by checking automatically for duplicate text sequences in the corpus. Another way to stop these kinds of errors is to carefully examine as a literary scholar the resources that are used (again) to create new data for computation. Additionally, as securing data quality falls under the responsibility of GLAM institutions and repositories' curators,

researchers should inform all interested parties about the defects they find. The enrichment of data turns out to be one of the most vital fields of cooperation between researchers and institutions sharing their expertise and knowledge.

Having the same kind of data stored in **different formats** likewise is a common problem with quality, correlated with using different resources. As an illustration: storing dates in multiple formats, like European Date (DD MM YYYY), US Date (MM DD YYYY), and Japan Date (YYYY MM DD).

It is also important to pay particular attention to the metadata format. **Metadata inconsistency** occurs when two comparable encodings follow different standards, e.g., researchers merging two separate CSV files or different libraries producing different headers in their TEI files.

The best approach is to keep a **data quality issues record**, ideally as an attachment to your data collection / creation log, so that you can monitor the problems and avoid errors. A plausible breakdown of a data quality issues log can be found for example [here](#). An entry contains a description of an issue, the people responsible for surmounting difficulties, and an approach adopted on the occasion. A log enables researchers to confirm the efficacy of data cleansing procedures and develop preventative measures (See: <https://www.yellowfinbi.com/best-practice-guide/data-preparation-enrichment-performance/data-quality>).

Rarely is data enrichment an isolated activity. Every data enrichment task needs to be

- repeatable i.e., consistently produce the desired outcomes
- rule-driven in order for researchers to be able to run it again and be certain of the same result each time as well as
- have a precise evaluation standard.

Take-home message: Data quality issues as well as repeatable, rule-driven, and evaluable enrichment procedures should be recorded in a special document, an extension of your data collection / creation log.

3.3.3. FAIR-ification

Finally, data enrichment and preparation may simply mean the **FAIR-ification** of data: i.e., making your data more FAIR. There are tools, supporting the principles of open science and FAIR and CARE, for example

<https://openrefine.org/>

which is an open-source program for handling unstructured data that can be used to clean up data and convert their formats, i.e. to deal with the issues listed in [3.3.2](#).

Open available automated FAIR metrics evaluation tools that help researchers to assess whether data they work with and publish comply with the FAIR Principles include: [FAIRAware](#), [SATIFYD](#), [the FAIR evaluator](#), [FAIR-Self-Check](#) by NFDI4Culture.

Take-home message: There are free and open-access tools that facilitate data enrichment and refinement before one embarks on sharing and linking data.

3.4. Data Analysis

Author: Michał Mrugalski

The act of analyzing or evaluating data can be characterized as validating hypotheses on corpora in relation to population or, in more exploratory approaches, testing preliminary insights into data patterns, e.g. observing how corpus elements cluster with regard to some predetermined features. Analysis is done with an eye toward a result. It aims at extracting **relevant information** from data. Data should therefore become as a result of the analysis interpretable information in a human-readable form, such as a report, table, visualization, etc. Or, to put it differently, computing turns data into information interesting and intelligible for humans.

In CLS, various analysis techniques are employed, frequently combined into a single project. These are:

- manual (human) data analysis: in CLS such an analysis is typically performed by a qualified team that annotates texts to give benchmark results for Machine Learning algorithms (for example: a group of previously instructed students decides whether a passage making part of a training data bears a narrative or a non-narrative character so that an algorithm can learn to classify in this regard texts)
- Electronic data analysis involves software that filters and reorganizes data, typically in the form of program packages for Machine Learning or, specifically, Natural Language Processing
- Generative A.I. data analysis uses Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning methods to classify and arrange data.

Machine Learning and Natural Language Processing, which can be regarded as an application of ML to language comprehension and text generation, are the main sources of research procedures for CLS. This relates to Optical Character Recognition (OCR) and text analysis (also known as text mining or content analysis). Text analysis can be categorized based on the language levels it considers:

- The morphological analysis, which, interesting in itself as it is for linguistics, CLS relegates to the pre-processing stage as it encompasses lemmatization, parts of speech tagging, and other procedures, regarded as preparatory (see [3.3.](#)),
- syntactic analysis or
- lexical semantics.

Especially the latter enjoys great popularity among CLS researchers as it includes Word Embeddings capturing inter-word relationships, Named Entity Recognition (NER), a prerequisite for automated network analysis and geographical analysis of literature, Sentiment Analysis, Topic

Modelling or Terminology Extraction. Higher levels include relational and discourse semantics and such advanced NLP applications as summarization and translation.

Whatever procedure one adopts, it is vital to keep a **laboratory log**, noting any manipulation of data alongside a reason for said manipulation, its author, and the point in time it happened. “Changing information in itself is not a problem. Difficulties arise when these modifications have not been documented or traced” (Desquilbet et al. 2019: 54).

Take-home message: analysis results in information extracted from data and presented in a human-comprehensible form. Needless to say, all procedures that data undergoes should be recorded.

3.5. Preserving and Publishing Data

Author: Carolin Odebrecht

The preservation and publication of CLS data represents the crucial step in the research data lifecycle for data users because it makes the results of the previous steps available for re-use. Publication enables data creators to publish data sets (corpora, collections, editions) in order to follow good research practices that require validation, reproducibility, and citability of research data (cf. [Section 3](#)). Data preservation is typically done by publication in a trustworthy repository.

Two aspects are important when publishing corpora: first the data set as such (Section [Data Set](#)) and the choice of the publication platform (Section [Publication Platform](#)). With the help of a to-do-list for data publication (Odebrecht and Biskup 2023) we aim to provide a helpful start for CLS data publications.

3.5.1. Data Set

Identify which version of a data set (title, version of the collection/corpus/edition, metadata) is eligible for publication. This data set needs to be completed by a README file containing the following information:

- Authors, contributors
- Contact person
- (References to) documentation(s)
- LICENSE statement
- Short introduction to data and software workflow
- Software and format dependencies
- Reference(s) to supplemental material(s)

A README is a type of brief documentation that is directly assigned to the data set and contains the necessary explanations and references for data (re-)use.

3.5.2. Publication platform

A publication platform is a service that stores, preserves, provides access to data sets including metadata and search / filtering functions via metadata catalogue. When evaluating publication services, we need to focus on domain-specific criteria related to research context of the service, user community and visibility in research discipline. The choice of publication platform depends on typically the following general criteria.

- Cost
- Membership / registration
- Terms of use
- Platform provider
- User support for publication or / and curation
- Formats
- (standard) metadata
- Persistent identifier
- Limitation to storage volume and time span
- Mode of access

Repositories can be found, e.g., by using the following meta search tools:

- [re3data](#)
- [Data Cite Repository Finder](#)
- [Roar Repository Finder](#)

In general, researchers can choose between generic (e.g. [Zenodo](#)), domain-specific repositories (e.g. [LAUDATIO-Repository](#), [Textgrid-Repository](#)) and institutional repositories which are services provided by computing centres and libraries of academic institutions. In this context, Harrower et al. (2020: 12): "Use disciplinary repositories where they exist, as they are more likely to be developed around domain expertise, disciplinary practices and community-based standards, which will promote the findability, accessibility, interoperability and ultimately the reuse and value of your data. The level of curation available in a repository is key to data quality and reusability."

In terms of quality assurance, the choice of a repository depends also on interfaces for data harvesting methods, standardised metadata that are compliant with DataCite Metadata Schema from OpenAIRE, ideally additional domain-specific metadata schemas and citation suggestions (Gouzi et al. 2024: 11-12).

Some certification instruments for data repositories have been developed, a prominent one being the [CoreTrustSeal](#) (CTS). At the same time, there are also data repositories that have no certification but have earned trustworthiness through many years of reliable operation by trustworthy providers and large user bases, like Zenodo.

Data publication allows for different use cases, illustrated by the examples described of this wiki: ELTeC (see [Section 3.1](#)) is organised as a community in zenodo:

<https://zenodo.org/communities/eltec/records>. DISCO (see [Section 3.1](#)) is published as an individual data set on Zenodo: <https://zenodo.org/records/7675512>. DraCor (see [Section 3.1](#)) aggregates texts from different repositories such as [Textgrid](#) (Textgrid Consortium 2006).

3.5.3. Generic Repository

A commonly used and trusted generic repository is [Zenodo](#) which is hosted by CERN.

- Cost: in general no costs for Open Access publication
- Membership / registration: Registration via [ORCID](#); [OpenAIRE](#), [GitHub](#) or registration via Zenodo itself.
- Terms of use: [Terms of use](#)
- Platform provider: [CERN](#)
- User support for publication or / and curation: via user [documentation](#) and [FAQ and contact information](#)
- Formats: no restrictions to formats
- (standard) metadata: compliant with [Data Cite Metadata](#)
- Persistent identifier: DOI for each version
- Limitation to storage volume and time span: Total files size limit per record is 50GB. Higher quotas can be requested and granted on a case-by-case basis.
- Mode of access: open and closed access

3.5.4. Publication Platform for Digital Edition

For digital editions, the interaction between data sets, visualisation, and exploration / filter mechanism are important. Therefore, data sets of a digital editions are often published not in data repositories but on specific platforms. Digital editions platforms are findable for example by Greta Franzini's [catalogue](#) or by Patrick Sahle's [catalogue](#).

The blog post of Marta Błaszczńska and Bartłomiej Szleszyński discuss in more depth issues concerning [digital scholarly editions and FAIR](#).

3.5.5. Licensing

Each publication needs a licence statement that ensures transparency for data (and software) re-use scenarios. With a licence, creators grant right to use their work. Importantly, if there is no right of use, there is no (re-)use.

For CLS data, copy right regulations often play a crucial role. Copy rights might be regulated on the national, European, or international level. The OpenAire project provides a [blog post](#) about how to licence my data. For re-using copy-right protected data, Andresen et al. (2023) provide a workflow.

3.6. Reusing Data

Author: Michał Mrugalski

The reuse of data lies at the core of the FAIR-ness and Open Science. Reusing data goes **both ways**. While reusing somebody else's data, researchers are encouraged to design their own data reuseable.

Whether looking for data or publishing one's own, a researcher is well advised to check whether a repository (potentially) containing data is certified by a **recognized standard** such as the [CoreTrustSeal](#).

The Registry of Research Data Repositories

- <https://www.re3data.org/>) is an intuitive place to start your search for a suitable repository to ingest or store your data. Searching databases by subject at
- <https://fairsharing.org/> likewise bodes well for a research project; this database contains items classified "Humanities and Social Sciences."

Another major source of data, which however may also assume the role of a storehouse for your results, are so called **GLAM** (Galleries, Libraries, Archives, and Museums) a.k.a. **Cultural Heritage Institutions** (CHI).

The [Heritage Data Reuse Charter](#) was developed by several European organizations (APEF, CLARIN, DARIAH, Europeana, E-RIHS) and European projects (Iperion-CH, PARTHENOS) with the goal of "designing a common environment that will enable all the relevant actors to work together to connect and improve access to heritage data" (Tóth-Czifra and Romary 2020: 2). The principles of

- reciprocity
- interoperability
- citability
- transparency
- stewardship, and
- reliability form the foundation of the environment.

"These principles are fully compliant with and map onto the FAIR principles and can be taken as their optimization for cultural heritage data exchange settings" (Tóth-Czifra and Romary 2020: 6).

These values materialize in **concrete situations** involving researchers and institutions; those situations demand that the **requirements** for data access and reuse as well as individual **accountability** for all decisions be specified. Thus, the paper "The Heritage Data Reuse Charter: from principles to research workflows" (Tóth-Czifra and Romary 2020) concludes with an [Annex](#) containing a questionnaire for researchers, CHI, and technical partners that addresses the principles and responsibilities, specifically:

- “Commitment concerning the re-use possibilities associated to source materials, future data sets and research publications built on them (Reciprocity, Openness)
- “Commitment to an agreed set of standards in terms of data sharing formats, processes and protocols (Interoperability)
- “Commitment to hosting and maintenance responsibilities (involving, if needed third party repositories) and best efforts to enabling the interconnectedness of source data (e.g. via PIDs or linked data protocols, their enrichments and the resulting publications (Stewardship)
- “Commitment to keep the richest possible track of documentation and provenance information (Trustworthiness)” (Tóth-Czifra and Romary 2020: 6)

It is recommended that researchers add the Charter’s principles to their **Data Management Plans**.

One of the most disputed aspects of data reuse is **entitlement**: the problem of data ownership implying licenses and other legal aspects, on which Tóth-Czifra et al. (2023: 56ff) expand in an engaging way, including the difference between Anglo-Saxon and Continental legal traditions concerning intellectual property.

Once more, those legal issues affect researchers during the data creation and publication processes. Working in closed spaces, like

- safe rooms, where researchers can access data on-site, or
- analysis portals, which are platforms that permit “approved analysis of data without allowing full access (viewing or downloading) or controlling where and who gets access” (https://open-science-training-handbook.github.io/Open-Science-Training-Handbook_EN/, section 2.2)

are two examples of places where work with restricted material can be carried out. Vivli, RAIRD, Corpuscle, Project Data Sphere, and INESS are a few virtual analysis portal examples. Another instance of how license and legal problems impact research practices furnishes the work with are

- derived text formats (“abgeleitete Textformate”, Schöch et al. 2020). In this case, the information on the corpus obtained through someone else’s analysis becomes the object of study in lieu of the initial corpus itself.

These limitations also apply to researchers that attempt to open their own data. Your best bet would be referring to the [CESSDA access categories for qualitative and quantitative data](#) and / or the [CLARIN licensing framework for language data](#). With four types of licenses (or even five, if we include CC0, which amounts to the renunciation of rights) and six possible combinations (Harrower et al. 2020: 23), the Creative Commons (CC) system is complicated. As a result, consulting a **license selector**, such as

- <https://chooser-beta.creativecommons.org/> or
- <https://ufal.github.io/public-license-selector/> could be a good solution.

One of the most important aspects of data reuse is appropriate **citation of data**; this can be a time-consuming process that involves organizing PIDs and tying together data from many sources. No wonder therefore that particular communities of interest such as [DataCite](#) work on facilitating the

process. The group formulated a set of best practices: [DataCite Best Practice Guide](#). A set of guidelines for citing data was developed by the Data Citation Synthesis Group (Data Citation Synthesis Group 2014). These citation forms ought to be machine-readable and intelligible to humans.

Take-home message: Data reusing is a two-way process that prompts researchers from the outset of a research project to shape their data as reusable, while at the same time recycling other people's data. The cooperation with stakeholders and other researchers alongside the problems of entitlement are thus at the heart of the research process in CLS, which turns out to be cooperative beyond the boundaries of a research team and their institutional affiliations.

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